

ISic3586

Honours for Marcus Iulius Philippus the younger

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

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Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2011.06.15

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Halaesa

Place of origin (modern)

near Castel di Tusa

Provenance

From the excavations in the agora in early 1970s

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Halaesa, Antiquarium e sito archeologico di Halaesa, inventory 30604

Physical Description

Twelve fragments of a grey marble slab with blue-grey veining. Eleven of the fragments connect, and have been joined together and fixed on a panel; the twelfth fragment, from the bottom left corner, does not join, but has been placed in approximate relation to the others on the same panel. Parts of all four sides of the original slab are preserved across the various fragments, and most of the upper half of the slab is preserved; the lower part of the slab is entirely lost, except for the bottom left hand corner (fragment 12). The outer edges of the slab have been crudely picked, either for setting the slab originally within a wall / monument, or perhaps for later reuse. Dimensions of the eleven joining fragments: height, 61.5 cm; width c.51 cm; depth c.3.5 cm. Fragment 12: height c.21 cm; width c.19.5 cm; depth c.4 cm.

Dimensions

Height greater than 61.5 cm

Width 51 cm

Depth 3.5 cm

Layout

Seven lines of Latin text are fully or partly preserved, filling the width of the stone, with a vacat above. Double guidelines are marked between each line.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

The letters are tall and fairly regular, V-cut between upper and lower guidelines (although they do not reach all the way to either guideline), with fairly pronounced serifs. M has straight, sloping hastae, with the middle point reaching to the bottom of the line; P is closed; E has a middle bar that is only slightly shorter than the top and bottom bars; C and O are fully rounded.

Letter heights:

Lines 1-7: 63-75 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation: Not measured mm

Text

1. M(arco) · Iulio [Phi]lip
2. [po] No[bi]lis
3. simo Caes(ari)
4. Imp(eratoris) · M(arci) · Iuli
5. [Philipp]i Pii ·
- undefined. [---]
6. []
7. (vac.undefined)D(ecreto)[D(ecurionum)][---]

Apparatus

Text from autopsy, after initial reconstruction by Scibona

Translation (en)

To Marcus Iulius Philippus, most noble Caesar, (son of) Emperor Marcus Iulius Philippus, Pius [---]. (Set up) by decree of the town councillors.

Commentary

It would be reasonable to expect some or all of Felicis Invicti Augusti filio to have stood in the lost portion of the inscription, since these are standard epithets of M. Iulius Philippus (see Peachin, M. 1990. Roman Imperial Titulature and Chronology, A.D. 235-284. Amsterdam: J.C. Gieben and Peachin, M. 1990. Roman Imperial Titulature and Chronology, A.D. 235-284. Amsterdam: J.C. Gieben), and the omission of the word filius would be unusual (it is unusual to delay it to the end of the full name of the father as must be the case here, but parallels can be cited, such as IRT no.48 [<http://inslib.kcl.ac.uk/irt2009/IRT048.html>]). It is, however, impossible to know how many lines are lost in the lacuna, and how standard or not this text may have been, given that some variation from the most common parallels is already visible, such as the omission of Caesar from the title of Philippus (pater) in line 4 (but see e.g. AE 1981 no.743 [www.trismegistos.org/text/190683]). On the other hand, it is unlikely that much more than the rest of the basic nomenclature of Philippus is missing. It is difficult to restore letters to the sequence of letter feet preserved at the start of the preserved line 6, but they are not incompatible with the titolature just noted, and the letters FIL would fit particularly well. The final letter on line 7 is clearly a D, and is clearly centred from the left margin, and so is most obviously compatible with the standard formula D(ecreto) D(ecurionum) of a public honorific. Links between Philippus the elder and the élite of the island are perhaps suggested by the fact that his fellow consul of 245 AD, C. Maesius Aquillius Fabius Titianus was a citizen of Thermae (ISic0092 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0092>] and ISic0093 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0093>] honour him and his son).

This text belongs between August 244 and August 247 AD (M. Iulius Philppus the younger as Caesar but not Augustus).

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Bibliography

Prag, J.R.W., Tigano, G. 2017. Alesa Archonidea : il lapidarium. *Introduzione all'archeologia di Halaesa*. Palermo. At no.30

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ΑΧΙΛΛΕΥΣ

ΠΡ
ΙΣ

ΠΑΡΜΕΝΙΔΟΥ
SIMOCLES
ΠΑΡΜΕΝΙΔΟΥ

ΠΙΤ-

ΠΑΡΜΕΝΙΔΟΥ
ΠΙΤ-

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